

Supplementary Materials

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1 Experimental settings

1.1 Instance construction

In the empirical study, 22 feature models, as shown in Table 1, are used to construct problem instances. These models are downloaded from the SPLOT repository [11]⁴, LVAT repository [12]⁵, and Dr. Li’s homepage⁶. All the models except Random-10000 are real and they represent practical systems, such as the web portal, banking software and Linux operating systems. The Random-10000, first introduced in [7], is a randomly generated feature model with 10,000 features. The feature models in Table 1 cover a wide range of sizes in terms of features, and feature model constraints. As seen, the number of features is 43 at least and 11,254 at most. The number of feature model constraints ranges from the smallest 68 to the largest 343,944. For each model, we can construct 2-, 3- and 4-objective problem instances. Therefore, we have $22 \times 3 = 66$ instances in total.

When creating instances, three resource constraints are imposed regardless of the number of objectives. Note that we randomly select 20 focused leaf features to define the third resource constraints. In practice, the resource limitation $l_j, j = 1, 2, 3$ is often determined by stakeholders based on their own situations/requirements. For the convenience of performing empirical studies, we manually set resource limitations following the practice in [5]. For each resource limitation, its formula and parameter settings are given in Table 2, where $V_j^{max}, j = 1, 2, 3$ is the upper bound of the corresponding resources; n_{tf} is the number of terminal features; $\rho_j \in (0, 1)$ is a control parameter. Note that V_1^{max}, V_2^{max} and V_3^{max} are actually the maximum value for the attributes *memory*, *cost* and *time*, respectively (see Table 1 in the main paper). The values of ρ_1, ρ_2 and ρ_3 are chosen based on our initial experiments. It was found that, by

⁴ SPLOT website: <http://www.splot-research.org/>

⁵ LVAT website: <http://code.google.com/p/linux-variability-analysis-tools>

⁶ Dr Li’s homepage: [https://www.cs.bham.ac.uk/~limx/Data/SIP\(data\).rar](https://www.cs.bham.ac.uk/~limx/Data/SIP(data).rar)

Table 1. Feature models used in this work.

FM	Features (#)	FM constraints (#)
WebPortal	43	68
SubseaControlSystem	142	374
printers	172	310
BankingSoftware	176	280
FQAs	178	347
android510	210	614
ubuntu1410	261	656
Ubuntu1204	263	682
E-shop	290	426
windows70	329	929
EIS	366	627
windows80	451	1,704
toybox	544	1,020
BigDataSystem	625	1,102
axTLS	684	2,155
freebsd-icse11	1,396	62,183
fiasco	1,638	5,228
uClinux	1,850	2,468
busybox-1.18.0	6,796	1,7836
2.6.28.6-icse11	6,888	343,944
Random-10000	10,000	14,296
uClinux-config	11,254	31,637

setting them to the values in Table 2, both feasible and infeasible solutions can be generated. This way, it makes the constructed constrained problem instances meaningful.

Table 2. Formulas and parameter values for calculating resource limitations.

Formula for resource limitation	Parameter values
$l_1 = V_1^{max} \times n_{tf} \times \rho_1$ (Memory limitation)	$V_1^{max} = 512, \rho_1 = 0.2$
$l_2 = V_2^{max} \times n_{tf} \times \rho_2$ (Cost limitation)	$V_2^{max} = 500, \rho_2 = 0.3$
$l_3 = V_3^{max} \times \rho_3$ (Time limitation)	$V_3^{max} = 500, \rho_3 = 0.9$

1.2 Population size and termination condition

The population size N in all the algorithms except C-NSGA-III is set to 100, 105 and 120 for 2-, 3- and 4-objective problem instances, respectively. This is due to the combination nature of possible weight vectors generated by the Das and Dennis’s systematic approach [3]. Because of a binary mating selection procedure, the population size in C-NSGA-III should be even [8]. Therefore, N is set to 106 for the 3-objective instances. Following the same practice in [6, 15], the maximum runtime allowed (or max_RT) is used as the termination condition. It is set to 3 seconds for feature models with less than 1,000 features, and to 30 second for freebsd-icse11, fiasco and uClinux following the suggestions in [15]. For the remaining models with more than 6,000 features, max_RT is set to 600 seconds.

1.3 Parameter settings in algorithms

In PMAD and its variants, there are some control parameters whose settings are given in Table 3. The first four parameters are common in decomposition-based algorithms, and their values are recommended in the literature [9, 16]. Therefore, we do not need a tuning phase. The fifth parameter R is set according to our initial experiments. By setting R to 10, the algorithm is able to obtain promising performance. For the peer algorithms in Section 2.3, i.e., SATVaEA [15], NSGA-II [4] and C-NSGA-III [8], they are free of control parameters. Notice that all the algorithms adopt two SAT solvers to repair solutions violating feature model constraints. Specifically, according to [14], an infeasible solution is repaired by calling either the probSAT solver [1] with a probability τ , or the SAT4J solver [2] with the probability $1 - \tau$. Following the suggestion in [14], τ is set to 0.9.

Table 3. Patenters settings in PMAD and its variants.

Parameter	Value	Description
T	$\lfloor 0.1N \rfloor$	Neighbor size
n_r	2	Maximum number of solutions to be replaced by a new solution
δ	0.9	Probability of selecting parents from neighbors
θ	5	Penalty term used in the PBI scalarizing function [16]
R	10	Weight vectors update period

2 Supplementary results

2.1 Effect of PM-based reproduction operators

Table 4 summarizes the pairwise comparisons between $SAR+EoD$ and each of the other two strategies. In this table, ‘ b ’, ‘ e ’ and ‘ w ’ denote the percentage of problem instances on which $SAR+EoD$ is significantly better than, statistically equal to, and significantly worse than the corresponding strategy, respectively. Note that the statistical testing is implemented by the Wilcoxon’s rank sum test [13] at a 0.05 significance level. For example, according to Table 4, $SAR+EoD$ performs significantly better than $Crossover+Mutation$ on 68% problem instances regarding HV. As can be found in Table 4, $SAR+EoD$ is better than the other two strategies on at least 59% and 65% instances concerning HV and IGD+, respectively. Inversely, $SAR+EoD$ performs worse on at most 30% instances in terms of HV, and 21% instances in terms of IGD+.

According to the above numerical results, $SAR+EoD$ is the best reproduction strategy, followed by $Crossover+EoD$ and then $Crossover+Mutation$. Moreover, the improvement of $SAR+EoD$ over the two strategies is significant. To

Table 4. Pairwise comparisons between $SAR+EoD$ and each of the other two strategies.

$SAR+EoD$ v.s.	HV			IGD+		
	b	e	w	b	e	w
$Crossover+Mutation$	68%	11%	21%	74%	11%	15%
$Crossover+EoD$	59%	11%	30%	65%	14%	21%

Fig. 1. Final solutions obtained by the three reproduction strategies on six representative 2-objective problem instances.

have a visual comparison, we given in Fig. 1 final solutions obtained by the three strategies on six representative 2-objective problem instances. As shown, $SAR+EoD$ converges better than the other two strategies on almost all of the selected problem instances, particularly on $axTLS$, $BigDataSystem$, $uClinux$ and $toybox$. Notably, the good convergence is not at the sacrifice of diversity. Indeed, it is observed that the solutions of $SAR+EoD$ are distributed widely along the approximated PF. Moreover, we present in Fig. 2 the solutions obtained on three representative 3-objective instances, i.e., $printers$, $BigDataSystem$ and $axTLS$. It can be seen that the solutions yielded by $SAR+EoD$ are distributed more diversely and uniformly than those yielded by both $Crossover+EoD$ and $Crossover+Mutation$ on all the three problem instances. For solutions obtained by the other two strategies, they either cover only a part of the front, or are not distributed uniformly (i.e., being dense on the boundary but spare at the central region).

Fig. 2. Final solutions obtained by the three reproduction strategies on three representative 3-objective problem instances.

2.2 Adaptive weight vectors make a difference

Fig. 3 presents final solutions obtained by *Without adaption* and *With adaption* on three representative 3-objective problem instances. Compared with the solutions of *Without adaption*, as shown clearly, those of *With adaption* are distributed more properly, without an obvious bias towards specific parts of the front. In contrast, the solutions obtained by *Without adaption* tend to concentrate on the boundary, leaving some central parts inadequately covered. According to parallel coordinates shown in Fig. 4, the above phenomenon is more evident on 4-objective problem instances. Parallel coordinates are widely used to visually show solutions in high (four or more) dimensional spaces, and they enable a partial evaluation of both convergence and diversity of a solution set [10]. As seen, in comparison with the solutions obtained by *With adaption*, those obtained by *Without adaption* are less diversified in each objective dimension on

the three instances, particularly on 2.6.28.6-icse11 and Random-10000. Indeed, many middle parts of each objective dimension are not covered by any solution.

Fig. 3. Final solutions obtained by *With adaption* and *Without adaption* on three representative 3-objective problem instances.

2.3 Overall performance evaluations

Fig. 5 gives solutions obtained by all the four algorithms on three representative instances with three objectives. For Ubuntu1204 and SubseaControlSystem, as shown clearly, the diversity of the solutions obtained by PMAD is much better than that of the solutions obtained by the others. For example, the solutions of PMAD are able to widely cover the approximated PF on Ubuntu1204, but those of the other algorithms fail. The PF of SubseaControlSystem is made up of four disconnected segments, and all the algorithms except PMAD cannot find adequate solutions on the first segment (from the left to the right). For uClinux-config, the largest feature model investigated in this study, it is observed that the solutions of PMAD are more effective than the other three algorithms in covering the boundary. As seen, SATVaEA, NSGA-II and C-NSGA-III can be only capable of finding solutions at the central region.

Fig. 4. Final solutions obtained by *With adaption* and *Without adaption* on three representative 4-objective problem instances.

Fig. 5. Final solutions obtained by all the algorithms on three representative 3-objective problem instances.

References

1. Balint, A., Schöning, U.: Choosing Probability Distributions for Stochastic Local Search and the Role of Make versus Break, pp. 16–29. International Conference on Theory and Applications of Satisfiability Testing, Berlin, Heidelberg (2012)
2. Berre, D.L., Parrain, A.: The Sat4j library, release 2.2, system description. *Journal on Satisfiability, Boolean Modeling and Computation* **7**, 59–64 (2010)
3. Das, I., Dennis, J.E.: Normal-boundary intersection: A new method for generating the pareto surface in nonlinear multicriteria optimization problems. *SIAM Journal on Optimization* **8**(3), 631–657 (1998)
4. Deb, K., Pratap, A., Agarwal, S., Meyarivan, T.: A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **6**(2), 182–197 (2002)
5. Guo, J., White, J., Wang, G., Li, J., Wang, Y.: A genetic algorithm for optimized feature selection with resource constraints in software product lines. *Journal of Systems & Software* **84**(12), 2208–2221 (2011)
6. Henard, C., Papadakis, M., Harman, M., Traon, Y.L.: Combining multi-objective search and constraint solving for configuring large software product lines. In: *The 37th International Conference on Software Engineering*. vol. 1, pp. 517–528 (May 2015)
7. Hierons, R.M., Li, M., Liu, X., Segura, S., Zheng, W.: SIP: Optimal Product Selection from Feature Models Using Many-Objective Evolutionary Optimization. *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology* **25**(2), 17:1–17:39 (Apr 2016)
8. Jain, H., Deb, K.: An evolutionary many-objective optimization algorithm using reference-point based nondominated sorting approach, part II: Handling constraints and extending to an adaptive approach. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **18**(4), 602–622 (2014)
9. Li, H., Zhang, Q.: Multiobjective optimization problems with complicated pareto sets, MOEA/D and NSGA-II. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **13**(2), 284–302 (2009)
10. Li, M., Zhen, L., Yao, X.: How to read many-objective solution sets in parallel coordinates. *IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine* **12**(4), 88–100 (2017)
11. Mendonca, M., Branco, M., Cowan, D.: S.P.L.O.T.: Software Product Lines Online Tools. In: *Proceedings of the 24th ACM SIGPLAN Conference Companion on Object Oriented Programming Systems Languages and Applications*. pp. 761–62. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1639950.1640002>
12. She, S., Lotufo, R., Berger, T., Wasowski, A., Czarnecki, K.: Reverse engineering feature models. In: *Proceedings of the 33rd International Conference on Software Engineering*. pp. 461–470. ICSE '11, ACM, New York, NY, USA (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1985793.1985856>
13. Wilcoxon, F.: Individual comparisons by ranking methods. *Biometrics bulletin* **1**(6), 80–83 (1945)
14. Xiang, Y., Yang, X., Zhou, Y., Huang, H.: Enhancing decomposition-based algorithms by estimation of distribution for constrained optimal software product selection. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **24**(2), 245–259 (2020)
15. Xiang, Y., Zhou, Y., Zheng, Z., Li, M.: Configuring Software Product Lines by Combining Many-Objective Optimization and SAT Solvers. *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology* **26**(4), 14:1–14:46 (Feb 2018)

16. Zhang, Q., Li, H.: MOEA/D: A multiobjective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **11**(6), 712–731 (2007)